

PHILOSOPHICAL MOMENTS: TEACHER INITIATED STRATEGY IN TEACHING PHILOSOPHY: A PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES EVALUATION AND BASIS FOR UTILIZATION AND ENHANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to evaluate the teacher innovated teaching strategy in teaching philosophy in the senior high school entitled “Philosophical Moments.” Specifically, the researchers wanted to confirm whether the said innovation utilizes the pedagogical approaches mandated by the R.A 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 in the implementation of the K 12 program. The process of evaluation is to correlate the pedagogical approaches employed by the teacher in teaching philosophy and the academic performance of the students in the subject. There were 64 grade 12 students who participated in the investigation composed of 19 males and 45 females. Descriptive data was analyzed using frequency and percentage, mean and standard deviation, while inferential data was statistically treated using the chi square method to determine the correlation between pedagogical approaches and academic performance in philosophy. The respondents rated the teachers’ pedagogical approaches utilization with high having collaborative and constructivist as the leading approaches. Most of the respondents are at an outstanding level in terms of academic performance in philosophy. The correlational analyses between the five pedagogical approaches and their academic performance in philosophy are deemed significant when tested at 0.05 level with the degree of freedom and tabular value of 12 and 21.03 respectively. Consequently, between the pedagogical approaches and academic performance yielded 40.43; 26.94; 33.38; 31.29 and 28.31 respectively, thus the researcher decided to accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis.

Keywords: *Philosophy, Pedagogical Approaches, Academic Performance, Collaborative, Constructivist, Inquiry Based, Integrative, Reflective*

INTRODUCTION

The primary goal of academic institution is to promote quality education regardless of the aspects whether on the content, content delivery, processes and human resources implications and involvement of all the stakeholders in the education cycle.

There are various initiatives undertaken by the different sectors and agencies both public and private. What is notable is the move of the Department of Education to add two more years in the Basic Education. Dinampo, Fatura & Paleracio (2024) in their article “correlating students personality types with curriculum exits in Paliparan Senior High School cited the Department of Education (2016) and claimed that more than a decade ago, the Department of Education The Department of Education (DepEd), led by former Secretary Armin Luistro, FSJ, introduced the K-to-12 program in 2011 and made kindergarten a prerequisite for basic education. In the 2012–2013 academic year, the Philippines introduced the K–12 Basic Education Program, which includes Kindergarten and 12 years of Basic Education. Republic Act No. 10533, also known as the Enhanced Basic Act of 2013, added two years of Senior High School (SHS) to the high school curriculum to better prepare students for postsecondary education.

The teaching of Philosophy in the Senior High School is challenging. For one, this is the first formal encounter of the students on the subject as a formal discipline after their junior high school years. The teacher needs to strike a balance between content and pedagogy to be able to deal with the subject matter smoothly. Though there are still issues on content in as far as the subject Introduction to the Philosophy of the Human Person, the researcher finds it also relevant to seek some appropriate approaches in carrying out its teaching task. According to Ganyaupfu (2013) philosophy as the general theory of education conceptualizes schools as a place where human beings, who have thoughts, feelings, cultures, and experiences, come to engage in personally meaningful learning.

Chan Robles (2013) emphasized the mandate from Republic Act 10533 also known as Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 section 5 which states that “curriculum implementation in the classroom should use pedagogical approaches such as constructivism, inquiry-based, reflective, collaborative, and integrative.”

In addition, Ampang (2023) affirmed the mandate by specifying that to be “reflective implies that the students make sense of their experiences by understanding the context of learning, their own contribution to that context, and by drawing from literature to explain these experiences.” Inquiry based means that the students are active participants in the learning process and is driven by their questions and innate curiosity.” Integrative implies that students learn in a way that curriculum content cuts across different learning areas and contexts.” Collaborative means students learn through working together with others to create knowledge and achieve shared learning goals.” Collaborative implies that the students construct their own knowledge, and their reality is determined by their own experiences.

Specifically, in the study of Cristea (2015) “underlines the specific study object, the specific normativity and the specific research methodology for *constructivist pedagogy*. *the specific study object of constructivist pedagogy* constitutes the difference between the inner system of the one who learns and the external environment *objective*, natural, community, cultural, civic, political, religious etc., at which the pupil refers to subjectively.” This means that constructivism as process helps the learner in giving analytical capability in constructing meaning based on what they have already experienced.

In another study about pedagogical approaches, Zhou, Chen & Chen (2019) explored and analyze the student perceptions of collaborative learning in teaching by conducting a field experiment in a Chinese public university. The quantitative results show that student perceptions were comprised of three dimensions: perceptions of collaborative learning, perceptions of teamwork, and perceptions of mobile learning.” The said finding likewise confirmed that to be effective in teaching collaborative learning must be utilized.

Further, in the study of Lee (2014) about the Inquiry teaching is characterized by its question-answer interactive information exchanges. Instead of learning passively, it stimulates students to actively engage in cognitive and discovery learning activities and found out that the students expressed enthusiasm on inquiry-based teaching and indicated that this approach reinforced their learning and understanding of the course material. Qualitative data also shows that inquiry-based teaching enhanced students’ classroom engagement and fostered an effective and meaningful learning experience.

Likewise, Kalimullin, Korshunova & Koinova-Zoellner (2016) studied the balance pedagogy as a methodological base for integrative-differentiated teaching of rural students and found out that balance pedagogy as a methodological base for integrative-differentiated teaching of rural schoolchildren and a means to improve the quality of education, personal and meta-subject results in rural schools.”

Furthermore, Navaneedhan (2010) studied about reflective teaching pedagogy as innovative approach in teacher education through open and distance learning to all teacher trainees were trained to adopt the reflective teaching-learning methodology during their teaching practice period and the result found out to be favorable as it reflected on their better academic performance.”

Studying about academic performance Jayalekshmi & Charles (2024) focused their attention on the impact of advanced pedagogical approaches on student performance in higher secondary schools and findings reveal a significant positive correlation between pedagogical approaches and student performance, emphasizing the importance of thoughtful instructional methods.”

On the other hand, the outbreak of Corona Virus (Sars COV2) as a pandemic have claimed millions of lives, social discomforts and has greatly disturbed our academic community. Its remnants have profoundly derailed students learning and left the scars of learning gaps and losses.

Initially, it shakes the entire academic community even to the point that some teachers got panicked and ask the natural existential question, “what do we do now”? However, to some, it forces us to cope up and consequently leads to material development. For me, the division led module writing activity wherein we have been given an opportunity to give our contribution to address the impact of the pandemic.

Every time the teacher step into the classroom to teach the subject, parallel existential question that keeps on lingering my mind, “what improvement do I need to make so that the material that was hurriedly done be improved?” What strategy in teaching philosophy that I need to employ so that the conceptual competencies in the subject be learned by my students who encountered the subject in the formal forum for the first time?”

Reflecting on those questions and with the opportunity of attending the National Educator’s Academy of the Philippines (NEAP) training entitled “Lunduyan sa Kahusayan,” together with the teaching endeavors in the classroom prompted this school-initiated capstone project which is called “Philosophical Moment.”

The “Philosophical Moments” is an approach in teaching philosophy using sound pedagogical approaches which is Reflective, Collaborative, Constructivist, Inquiry-Based, and Integrative (R2C2I). It is guided by Pragmatic, Existential and Empiricists school of Thought as its philosophical lenses. The class is divided into different groups who shall act as facilitator in every meeting in collaboration with the subject teacher and with fellow students.

Research Questions

This study aims to evaluate the alignment of “Philosophical Moments” as a teaching strategy in the subject “Introduction to the Philosophy of the Human Person to the different pedagogical approaches. It also explores its classroom usage and its impact on the academic performance of the students and creates some recommendations that are intended to fine tune its activities.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of teacher’s usage of the pedagogical approaches in teaching philosophy as perceived by the students in terms of:
 - a. Constructivist
 - b. Collaborative
 - b. Integrative
 - c. Inquiry Based; and
 - d. Reflective?
2. What is the level of Academic Performance of the Students in Philosophy?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the pedagogical approaches usage as perceived by the students and their academic performance in Philosophy?

4. Based on the findings what intervention can I recommend improving “Philosophical Moments,” as a teacher-initiated intervention in teaching philosophy?

METHODOLOGY

The subjects of the study are grade 12 students at Dr Jose P. Rizal Senior High School in the subject “Introduction to the Philosophy of the Human Person.” Particularly, they are the sections whom the Philosophical Moments strategy was practiced. The school is a public, “stand alone” senior high school located at Sto. Cristo, Dasmariñas City, Cavite. It was participated by 64 students composed of 19 males and 45 females. Purposive stratified sampling was used since all the respondents belonged to the sections whom Philosophical Moments strategy was used.

The researcher adapted the instrument used in the study of Ampang (2023) in his study entitled “Pedagogical Approaches and Challenges among Teachers in the Implementation of the K-12 Curriculum in the Division of Maguindanao.” The instrument on pedagogical approaches was composed of 20 items arranged randomly. The researcher made some modification to arrange the questionnaire according to the approaches wherein numbers 1 to 4 is about the constructivist pedagogy; 5 to 8 is collaborative; 9 to 12 is about inquiry based; 13 to 15 is integrative; and 16 to 20 is about the reflective pedagogy. Likewise, instead of using checklist version the one of the researchers modified it and added a Likert scale to determine the extent of pedagogical approaches usage.

The new instrument version is called Pedagogical Approaches Usage Survey-Dinampo (2024) version. Before the survey was conducted, permission to conduct the study from the school head is sought together with the access of the student grades in philosophy through the Students Electronic Records Management System (SERMS) accessed from the records office. The descriptive data was analysed using simple frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. The inferential data was analysed using chi square statistics.

Table 1: The Respondents of the Study

SEX	ABM 12 A		HUMSS 12 C		TOTAL	
	FREQUENCY	%	FREQUENCY	%	FREQUENCY	%
MALE	3	13	16	39	19	29.7
FEMALE	20	87	25	61	45	70.3
TOTAL	23	100	41	100	64	100

Table 1 shows that there were 3 or 13 percent and 20 or 87 percent of the respondents who were male and female from the Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM) section respectively. In addition, there were 16 or 39 percent and 25 or 61 percent who were from the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) section. In total, there were 19 or 29.70 males and 45 or 70.30 percent were females.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: The Level Pedagogical Approaches Usage

Pedagogical Approaches	Mean	SD	Verbal interpretation	Rank
Collaborative	2.93	1.02	High	1
Constructivist	2.88	1.02	High	2
Inquiry Based	2.87	0.99	High	3
Reflective	2.79	0.97	High	4
Integrative	2.78	0.97	High	5

Table 2 shows the level of the pedagogical approaches used by the teacher in the classroom in teaching philosophy as seen by the students. Collaborative pedagogical approach got the mean of 2.93 and a standard deviation of 1.02 with a high level in terms of verbal description and ranked first in terms of their mean. On the other hand, constructivist pedagogical approach got the mean of 2.88 and a standard deviation of 1.02 with a verbal description which is high and ranked second among the pedagogical approaches' usage.

In the same manner, inquiry based got the mean of 2.87 and a standard deviation of 0.99 which is also high in terms of verbal description and ranked 3 among the pedagogical approaches utilized by the teacher in teaching philosophy.

In addition, reflective got the mean of 2.79 and a standard deviation of 0.97 which is verbally categorized as high and ranked fourth among the pedagogical approaches.

Lastly, integrative got the mean of 2.78 and standard deviation of 0.97 which is likewise described as high and ranked fifth among the pedagogical approaches that is used by the teacher in teaching philosophy.

This means that collaborative pedagogy is a notable strategy that is used by the teacher as seen from the perspective of the students with very slight margin lead over the other pedagogical approaches. Likewise, it is worthwhile to note that all the pedagogical approaches registered on a high level in terms of pedagogical approaches usage.

Table 3: The Level of Academic Performance of Students in Philosophy

Academic Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	27	42.19
Very Satisfactory	13	20.31
Satisfactory	10	15.63
Fairly Satisfactory	7	10.94
Did Not Meet Expectation	7	10.94
Total	64	100

Table 3 above shows the level of academic performance of the students in their subject "Introduction to the Philosophy of the Human Person." Among the respondents there were 27 or 42.19 percent got an outstanding grade, while 13 or 20.31 among them got a very satisfactory grade, 10 or 15.63 percent of the students got a satisfactory performance and 7 or 10.94 percent among them are "fairly satisfactory" and "did not meet expectation" in their subject academic performance respectively.

This means that majority of the respondents got an outstanding performance in terms of their grades in philosophy.

Table 4: Correlation Between Constructivist and Academic Achievement

	VERY HIGH		HIGH		LOW		VERYLOW		TOTAL
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Outstanding	23	13.92	2	4.22	1	4.22	1	4.64	27
Very Satisfactory	7	6.70	4	2.03	1	2.03	1	2.23	13
Satisfactory	1	5.16	2	1.56	5	1.56	2	1.72	10
Fairly Satisfactory	1	3.61	1	1.09	2	1.09	3	1.20	7
Did Not Meet Expectation	1	3.61	1	1.09	1	1.09	4	1.20	7
TOTAL	33		10		10		11		64
DF = 12	$x^2_{tab} = 21.32$		$x^2_{comp} = 40.43$		Significant at 0.05 level				

Table 4 shows the correlation between the constructivist pedagogical approach and the academic performance in philosophy. Further, it reveals that in the outstanding and very high level it obtained an observed frequency of 23 and the expected frequency is 13.92, while between the outstanding and high obtained and observed frequency of 2 with an expected frequency of 4.22, however, in the outstanding and low level has the observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 4.22, while in the outstanding and very low level got the frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 4.64.

The same table reveals that between the very satisfactory and very high level it garnered an observed frequency of 7 and an expected frequency of 6.70, while between the very satisfactory and high level obtained an observed frequency of 4 and an expected frequency of 2.03; in the same manner between got the very satisfactory and the low level obtained an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 2.03, while between

the very satisfactory and the very low level got the observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 2.23.

In addition, between satisfactory and very high level registered an observed frequency of 1 and an expected frequency of 5.16, while the satisfactory and high level got the observed frequency of 2 with an expected frequency of 1.56, in the same manner on the satisfactory and low level obtained an observed frequency of 5 with an expected frequency of 1.56 and between satisfactory and very low level got an observed frequency of 2 with an expected frequency of 1.72.

Further, between fairly satisfactory and very high level got an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 3.61 while between fairly satisfactory and high level obtained an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 1.09, likewise between fairly satisfactory and low level registered an observed frequency of 2 with an expected frequency of 1.09 and between fairly satisfactory and very low level acquired and observed frequency of 3 with and expected frequency of 1.20.

Furthermore, between did not meet expectation and very high level got an observed frequency of 1 with and expected frequency of 3.61 while did not meet expectation and high level, low level both obtained an observed frequency of 1 with and expected frequency of 1.09 respectively and in the same manner between did not meet expectation and very low level registered an observed frequency and an expected frequency of 4 and 1.20 respectively.

Consequently, the chi square computation obtained a computed value of 40.43 which is higher than the tabular value of 21.03 using 12 as its calculated degree of freedom. This means that the correlation between the constructivist pedagogy as rated by the students and their academic performance in philosophy is significant. Thus, the decision of the researcher is to accept the alternative and reject the null hypothesis.

Table 5: Correlation Between Collaborative and Academic Achievement

	VERY HIGH		HIGH		LOW		VERYLOW		TOTAL
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Outstanding	23	15.61	1	2.53	1	2.95	2	5.91	27
Very Satisfactory	9	7.52	2	1.22	1	1.42	1	2.84	13
Satisfactory	2	5.78	1	0.94	3	1.09	4	2.19	10
Fairly Satisfactory	2	4.05	1	0.66	1	0.77	3	1.53	7
Did Not Meet Expectation	1	4.05	1	0.66	1	0.77	4	1.53	7
TOTAL	37		6		7		14		64

DF = 12 $\chi^2_{tab} = 21.03$ $\chi^2_{comp.} = 21.03$ Significant at 0.05 level

Table 5 shows the correlation between the collaborative pedagogical approach and the academic performance in philosophy. Further, it reveals that in the outstanding and very high level it obtained an observed frequency of 23 and the expected frequency

is 15.61, while between the outstanding and high got an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 2.53, however, in the outstanding and low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 2.95, while in the outstanding and very low level acquired an observed frequency and an expected frequency of 2 and 5.91 respectively.

The same table reveals that between the very satisfactory and very high level garnered an observed frequency of 9 and an expected frequency of 7.52, while between the very satisfactory and high level obtained an observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 1.22; in the same manner between very satisfactory and the low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 1.42, while between very satisfactory and the very low level acquired and observed and expected frequency of 1 and 2.84 respectively.

In addition, between satisfactory and very high level registered an observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 5.78, while between the satisfactory and high level got the observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 0.94, in the same manner, on the satisfactory and low level obtained an observed frequency of 3 with an expected frequency of 1.09 and between satisfactory and very low level earned an observed and expected frequency of 4 and 2.19 respectively.

Further, between fairly satisfactory and very high level got an observed frequency of 2 with an expected frequency of 4.05 while between fairly satisfactory and high level obtained an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 0.66, likewise between fairly satisfactory and low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 0.77 and lastly, between fairly satisfactory and very low level acquired an observed frequency and expected of 3 and 1.53 respectively.

Furthermore, between did not meet expectation and very high level got an observed frequency of 1 with and expected frequency of 4.05 while did not meet expectation and high level obtained and observed frequency 1 with an expected frequency of 0.66, in the same manner, between did not meet expectation and low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with and expected frequency of 0.77 and lastly, between did not meet expectation and very low level earned an observed and expected frequency of 4 and 1.53 respectively.

Consequently, the chi square computation obtained a computed value of 26.94 which is higher than the tabular value of 21.03 using 12 as its calculated degree of freedom. This means that the correlation between the collaborative pedagogy as rated by the students and their academic performance in philosophy is significant. Thus, the decision of the researcher is to accept the alternative and reject the null hypothesis

Table 6: Correlation Between Inquiry Based and Academic Achievement

	VERY HIGH		HIGH		LOW		VERYLOW		TOTAL
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Outstanding	23	15.19	1	2.95	1	4.22	2	4.64	27
Very Satisfactory	8	7.31	3	1.42	1	2.03	1	2.23	13
Satisfactory	2	5.63	1	1.09	5	1.56	2	1.72	10
Fairly Satisfactory	2	3.94	1	0.77	2	1.09	2	1.20	7
Did Not Meet Expectation	1	3.94	1	0.77	1	1.09	4	1.20	7
TOTAL	36		7		10		11		64

DF = 12 $\chi^2_{tab} = 21.32$ $\chi^2_{comp} = 38.38$ Significant at 0.05 level

Table 6 shows the correlation between the inquiry based pedagogical approach and the academic performance in philosophy. Further, it reveals that in the outstanding and very high level obtained an observed frequency of 23 and the expected frequency is 15.19, while between the outstanding and high got an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 2.95, however, in the outstanding and low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 4.22, while in the outstanding and very low level acquired an observed frequency and an expected frequency of 2 and 4.64 respectively.

The same table reveals that between the very satisfactory and very high level garnered an observed frequency of 8 and an expected frequency of 7.31, while between the very satisfactory and high level obtained an observed frequency of 3 and an expected frequency of 1.42, in the same manner between very satisfactory and the low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 2.03, while between very satisfactory and the very low level acquired and observed and expected frequency of 1 and 2.23 respectively.

In addition, between satisfactory and very high level registered an observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 5.63, while between the satisfactory and high level got the observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 1.09, in the same manner, on the satisfactory and low level obtained an observed frequency of 5 with an expected frequency of 1.56 and between satisfactory and very low level earned an observed and expected frequency of 2 and 1.72 respectively.

Further, between fairly satisfactory and very high level got an observed frequency of 2 with an expected frequency of 3.94 while between fairly satisfactory and high level obtained an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 0.77, likewise between fairly satisfactory and low level registered an observed frequency of 2 with an expected frequency of 1.09 and lastly, between fairly satisfactory and very low level acquired an observed frequency and expected of 2 and 1.20 respectively.

Furthermore, between did not meet expectation and very high level got an observed frequency of 1 with and expected frequency of 3.94 while did not meet expectation and high level obtained and observed frequency of 1 with an expected

frequency of 0.77, in the same manner, between did not meet expectation and low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with and expected frequency of 1.09 and lastly, between did not meet expectation and very low level earned an observed and expected frequency of 4 and 1.20 respectively.

Consequently, the chi square computation obtained a computed value of 33.38 which is higher than the tabular value of 21.03 using 12 as its calculated degree of freedom. This means that the correlation between the inquiry-based pedagogy as rated by the students and their academic performance in philosophy is significant. Thus, the decision of the researcher is to accept the alternative and reject the null hypothesis.

Table 7: Correlation Between Integrative and Academic Performance

	VERY HIGH		HIGH		LOW		VERY LOW		TOTAL
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Outstanding	21	13.08	4	5.06	1	2.95	1	5.91	27
Very Satisfactory	6	6.30	5	2.44	1	1.42	1	2.84	13
Satisfactory	2	4.84	1	1.88	3	1.09	4	2.19	10
Fairly Satisfactory	1	3.39	1	1.31	1	0.77	4	1.53	7
Did Not Meet Expectation	1	3.39	1	1.31	1	0.77	4	1.53	7
TOTAL	31		12		7		14		64
DF = 12	$x^2_{tab} = 21.32$		$x^2_{comp} = 31.29$		Significant at 0.05 level				

Table 7 shows the correlation between the integrative pedagogical approach and the academic performance in philosophy. Further, it reveals that in the outstanding and very high level obtained an observed frequency of 21 and the expected frequency is 13.08, while between the outstanding and high got an observed frequency of 4 with an expected frequency of 5.06, however, in the outstanding and low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 2.95, while in the outstanding and very low level acquired an observed frequency and an expected frequency of 1 and 5.91 respectively.

The same table reveals that between the very satisfactory and very high level garnered an observed frequency of 6 and an expected frequency of 6.30, while between the very satisfactory and high level obtained an observed frequency of 5 and an expected frequency of 2.44, in the same manner between very satisfactory and the low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 1.42, while between very satisfactory and the very low level acquired and observed and expected frequency of 1 and 2.84 respectively.

In addition, between satisfactory and very high level registered an observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 4.84, while between the satisfactory and high level got the observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 1.88, in the same manner, on the satisfactory and low level obtained an observed frequency of 3 with

an expected frequency of 1.09 and between satisfactory and very low level earned an observed and expected frequency of 4 and 2.19 respectively.

Further, between fairly satisfactory and very high level got an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 3.39 while between fairly satisfactory and high level obtained an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 1.31, likewise between fairly satisfactory and low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 0.77 and lastly, between fairly satisfactory and very low level acquired an observed frequency and expected of 4 and 1.53 respectively.

Furthermore, between did not meet expectation and very high level got an observed frequency of 1 with and expected frequency of 3.39 while did not meet expectation and high level obtained and observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 1.31, in the same manner, between did not meet expectation and low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with and expected frequency of 0.77 and lastly, between did not meet expectation and very low level earned an observed and expected frequency of 4 and 1.53 respectively.

Consequently, the chi square computation obtained a computed value of 31.29 which is higher than the tabular value of 21.03 using 12 as its calculated degree of freedom. This means that the correlation between the integrative pedagogy as rated by the students and their academic performance in philosophy is significant. Thus, the decision of the researcher is to accept the alternative and reject the null hypothesis.

Table 8: Correlation Between Reflective and Academic Performance

	VERY HIGH		HIGH		LOW		VERYLOW		TOTAL
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	
Outstanding	20	13.08	5	4.64	1	3.38	1	5.91	27
Very Satisfactory	7	6.30	3	2.23	2	1.63	1	2.84	13
Satisfactory	2	4.84	1	1.72	3	1.25	4	2.19	10
Fairly Satisfactory	1	3.39	1	1.20	1	0.88	4	1.53	7
Did Not Meet Expectation	1	3.39	1	1.20	1	0.88	4	1.53	7
TOTAL	31		11		8		14		64
DF = 12	$\chi^2_{tab} = 21.03$		$\chi^2_{comp} = 28.31$		Significant at 0.05 level				

Table 8 shows the correlation between the reflective pedagogical approach and the academic performance in philosophy. Further, it reveals that in the outstanding and very high level obtained an observed frequency of 20 and the expected frequency is 13.08, while between the outstanding and high got an observed frequency of 5 with an expected frequency of 4.64, however, in the outstanding and low level registered an observed frequency of 2 with an expected frequency of 1.63, while in the outstanding and very low level acquired an observed frequency and an expected frequency of 1 and 2.84 respectively.

The same table reveals that between the very satisfactory and very high level garnered an observed frequency of 7 and an expected frequency of 6.30, while between the very satisfactory and high level obtained an observed frequency of 3 and an expected frequency of 2.23, in the same manner between very satisfactory and the low level registered an observed frequency of 2 with an expected frequency of 1.63, while between very satisfactory and the very low level acquired and observed and expected frequency of 1 and 2.84 respectively.

In addition, between satisfactory and very high level registered an observed frequency of 2 and an expected frequency of 4.84, while between the satisfactory and high level got the observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 1.72, in the same manner, on the satisfactory and low level obtained an observed frequency of 3 with an expected frequency of 1.25 and between satisfactory and very low level earned an observed and expected frequency of 4 and 2.19 respectively.

Further, between fairly satisfactory and very high level got an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 3.39 while between fairly satisfactory and high level obtained an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 1.20, likewise between fairly satisfactory and low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 0.88 and lastly, between fairly satisfactory and very low level acquired an observed frequency and expected of 4 and 1.53 respectively.

Furthermore, between did not meet expectation and very high level got an observed frequency of 1 with and expected frequency of 3.39 while did not meet expectation and high level obtained and observed frequency of 1 with an expected frequency of 1.20, in the same manner, between did not meet expectation and low level registered an observed frequency of 1 with and expected frequency of 0.88 and lastly, between did not meet expectation and very low level earned an observed and expected frequency of 4 and 1.53 respectively.

Consequently, the chi square computation obtained a computed value of 28.31 which is higher than the tabular value of 21.03 using 12 as its calculated degree of freedom. This means that the correlation between the reflective pedagogy as rated by the students and their academic performance in philosophy is significant. Thus, the decision of the researcher is to accept the alternative and reject the null hypothesis

Conclusions

Based on the findings from the data analysis, the pedagogical approaches used by the teacher as seen by the students and their academic performance in philosophy is significantly and proportionally correlated. This means that the higher the pedagogical approaches usage will likewise yield a higher academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings and conclusion the researcher opts to recommend the following:

1. Teachers need to utilize the pedagogical approaches in their classroom to yield the expected results that is outlined in the K to 12 curriculum program and other related strategies that creates a conducive learning environment for the students.
2. School heads, Master Teachers, Head Teachers and other personalities who oversee, monitor and supervise the teaching and learning process shall assure that all these pedagogical approaches are really applied in the classroom.
3. To the Department of Education family, that the supervising might be realistic if more items be created for instructional leadership positions so that overseeing, monitoring and supervision will be carried out faithfully and realistically.
4. To the Human Resource of the Department of Education, that there will be more direct and realistic trainings for teachers on the different pedagogical approaches.
5. To the future researchers, that they can conduct a more thorough research investigations preferably but not limited to experimental and longitudinal study about the application of these pedagogical approaches in the classroom.
6. More co-curricular activities may be provided in the different schools related to the different curriculum programs and levels.
7. The researcher highly recommends the use of "Philosophical Moments in teaching philosophy and can be a model for adaptation in teaching other subjects as well.
8. Learning Materials can be developed using the model.
9. Lesson planning can use the philosophical moment model as complete procedures and processes in the teaching and learning process.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Attached to the survey questionnaire was the informed consent form wherein selected respondents were invited to participate in the study. They were asked to complete the few questions relevant to the variables under study. They are assured that the information gathered are kept confidential. In the records the respondents name will not be associated with their answers. Participation was voluntary, and they may withdraw from the survey anytime or may decline to answer any questions that make them uncomfortable. They were given enough time to answer the question the answers are treated with utmost confidentiality and will be used for academic purposes only. The information gathered will be handled properly under the provisions of Republic Act 10173 of the Data Privacy Act of 2022.

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